

1 **MANual vs. automatIC Local Activation Time Annotation for Guiding**
2 **Premature Ventricular Complex Ablation Procedures**
3 **(MANIaC-PVC Study)**

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32 **ABSTRACT**

33 **Aims:** To assess potential benefits of a local activation time (LAT) automatic acquisition
34 protocol using WF annotation plus an ECG pattern matching algorithm (AUT-arm) during
35 PVC ablation procedures.

36 **Methods:** Prospective, randomized, controlled and international multicenter study
37 (NCT03340922). 100 consecutive patients with indication for PVC ablation were enrolled and
38 randomized to AUT (n=50) or MAN (n=50) annotation protocols using the CARTO3
39 navigation system. The primary endpoint was mapping success. Clinical success was defined
40 as a PVC-burden reduction of $\geq 80\%$ in the 24-h Holter within 6 months after the procedure.

41 **Results:** Mean age was 56 ± 14 years, 54% men. The mean baseline PVC burden was $25\pm 13\%$,
42 and mean LVEF $55\pm 11\%$. Baseline characteristics were similar between the groups. The most
43 frequent PVC-SOO were RVOT (41%), LV (25%), and LVOT (17%), without differences
44 between groups. RF time and number of RF applications were similar for both groups.
45 Mapping and procedure times were significantly shorter in the AUT-arm (25.5 ± 14.3 min vs.
46 32.8 ± 12.6 min, $p=0.009$; and 54.8 ± 24.8 min vs. 67.4 ± 25.2 , $p=0.014$, respectively), while
47 more mapping points were acquired [136 (94–222) AUT vs. 79 (52–111) MAN; $p<0.001$].
48 Mapping and clinical success were similar in both groups. There were no procedure-related
49 complications.

50 **Conclusion:** The use of a complete automatic protocol for LAT annotation during PVC
51 ablation procedures allows to achieve similar clinical endpoints with higher procedural
52 efficiency when compared to conventional, manual annotation carried out by expert operators.

53

54 **KEYWORDS**

55 Premature ventricular complexes; catheter ablation; local activation time; automatic
56 annotation; wavefront; activation mapping.

57 **WHAT'S NEW?**

- 58 • A fully automatic acquisition of electroanatomical maps (EAM) during premature
59 ventricular complex (PVC) ablation procedures is feasible, using wavefront for local
60 activation time (LAT) annotation and an ECG pattern matching algorithm to precisely
61 identify the clinical PVC.
- 62 • Compared to manual activation mapping carried out by expert operators, this
63 automatic approach accurately identifies the ablation target point, reaching similar
64 clinical outcomes.
- 65 • The automatic acquisition of EAM during PVC ablation procedures permits to
66 improve procedures' efficiency in terms of mapping time, procedure time, and density
67 of the acquired maps.

68 **INTRODUCTION**

69 Catheter ablation is an accepted and effective treatment strategy for management of premature
70 ventricular complexes (PVCs). Conventional PVC mapping requires experience performing
71 real-time interpretation of local signals and annotating the local activation time (LAT) in
72 unipolar (U-EGM) and/or bipolar electrograms (B-EGM). However, the major disadvantages
73 of U-EGMs are susceptibility to noise and the presence of substantial far-field signal,¹ which
74 limit their routine use during activation mapping for some substrates. Drawbacks to B-EGMs
75 include being influenced by wavefront direction, bipole orientation, electrode size, and
76 interelectrode spacing.² Furthermore, LAT assessment on B-EGMs is often challenging,
77 especially in cases with low-voltage EGMs with multiple components. Recently, El Haddad et
78 al described an automated algorithm that detects the maximal $-dV/dt$ in the U-EGM within
79 the window demarcated by the B-EGM that achieved the highest accuracy in algorithmic
80 mapping of atrial and ventricular tachycardia.³ A recent study⁴ showed a good correlation
81 between manual and automatic LAT annotation systems. However, data about its utility,
82 accuracy in PVC ablation procedures, and its clinical impact are scarce.

83 The present randomized study aims to analyze the accuracy of this novel algorithmic method
84 (Wavefront, CARTO3[®], Biosense Webster, Diamond Bar, CA, USA) together with the use of
85 an automatic ECG pattern recognition algorithm, by comparison with conventional manual
86 annotation and visual PVC-ECG recognition in a multicenter cohort of patients referred for
87 PVC ablation.

88 **METHODS**

89 **Patient sample and randomization**

90 This is a prospective, randomized, controlled and international multicenter study
91 (NCT03340922), including 100 consecutive patients referred for a first PVC ablation. One
92 hundred and fifty consecutive patients were initially recruited in 4 centers. Forty patients
93 (27%) had to be excluded due to a very low burden of PVCs (< 1 PVC/min)⁵ during cardiac
94 monitoring before the procedure, being targeted by pace-mapping. Nine patients (6%) could
95 not be ablated due to complete absence of PVCs. One patient was not ablated after
96 documenting a para-Hisian SOO. Finally, 100 patients were included for analysis. All patients
97 were randomized on a 1:1 basis to each of the LAT annotation methods before the ablation
98 procedure: i) AUT-method, using wavefront annotation plus an automatic ECG pattern
99 recognition algorithm, and ii) MAN-method, using real-time manual annotation by an expert
100 operator (cardiac electrophysiologist with at least 5-year experience), plus visual inspection of
101 the ECG to acquire points whenever the PVC of interest is observed (figure 1).

102 Age < 18 years, repeated procedures, a low burden of PVCs during the procedure (< 1 PVC
103 per minute),⁵ pregnancy, presence of concomitant investigation treatments, or patient's
104 refusal to participate in the study, were exclusion criteria. The study complied with the
105 Declaration of Helsinki. The local Ethics Committee approved the study protocol and all
106 included participants signed the informed consent.

107

108 **Definitions and endpoints**

109 Mapping success was defined as complete PVC abolition after RF applications at the earliest
110 activation site (EAS) identified using the assigned mapping method. A maximum of 2 RF
111 applications with appropriate parameters (as detailed later) during a maximum of 45 seconds
112 were allowed. Acute procedure success was defined as complete elimination of the PVC at

113 the end of the procedure. A target point for ablation was defined as any suspected PVC-site of
114 origin (SOO), based on the identified EAS, where RF was delivered according to mapping
115 data. The maximum distance between 2 RF applications to be considered as delivered at the
116 same target point was defined as 5 mm. ⁶ Clinical success was defined as the PVC-burden
117 reduction of $\geq 80\%$ in a 24-h Holter performed within 6 months after the procedure, since
118 recurrences can be usually detected during this time period. ⁷

119 The primary endpoint was mapping success using the assigned mapping approach, as
120 previously defined. Mapping time, number of mapped chambers and points, number of target
121 points, RF time, number of RF applications, acute procedure success, and clinical success
122 were considered secondary endpoints of the study.

123

124 **Activation mapping and annotation methods**

125 Electroanatomical mapping (EAM) was performed using the CARTO3[®] navigation system
126 (Biosense Webster, Irvine, CA, USA) with a 3.5-mm irrigated tip catheter (NaviStar[®]
127 ThermoCool[®] or ThermoCool[®] SmartTouch[®], Biosense Webster). During the procedure,
128 12-lead surface ECG and intracardiac recordings were displayed by an electrophysiology data
129 acquisition system (Bard LabSystem, CR Bard Inc, Lowell, MA, USA; or EP-Tracer,
130 CardioTek, Maastricht, The Netherlands).

131 A detailed activation map of the cardiac chamber/s suspected to contain the PVC-SOO was
132 performed in all patients. If an outflow tract (OT) origin was suspected, the mapped chamber
133 was selected by a pre-defined algorithm (figure 2) including a previously described clinical
134 score (1 point for each of the following: hypertension, male gender, age > 50 years) together
135 with ECG criteria. ⁸ The minimum density of points required to obtain an acceptable map was
136 defined as a fill threshold of ≤ 6 mm in the 10-ms isochronal area containing the earliest
137 activation site (area of interest), and ≤ 10 mm for the complete map.

138 An ECG surface lead with a well-defined (not bimodal) R-wave peak (R peak = 0 ms) was
139 used as the reference to perform the activation EAM. For both annotation methods, the end of
140 the window of interest was set at the end of the PVC-QRS to avoid the annotation of atrial
141 far-field signals (in cases with retrograde conduction of the PVC). During activation mapping,
142 points were acquired only after a 2-second period of catheter stability.

143 Activation mapping of additional anatomical structures was allowed under operator criteria, in
144 cases where the suspected SOO could not be identified at the initially mapped chamber. The
145 earliest activation site (EAS) was considered to be located at the point with the earliest LAT
146 relative to the onset of PVC on the 12-lead surface ECG, when activation mapping was
147 concluded.

148

149 *Manual annotation (MAN-method)*

150 Manual annotation was performed in real time by an experienced electrophysiologist.
151 Mapping points were acquired under operator's criteria after real-time visual inspection of the
152 PVC-QRS morphology. LAT of every acquired point was measured from the onset of B-
153 EGM (earliest positive or negative deflection) of the distal bipole of the mapping catheter to
154 the defined reference. The U-EGM was used to identify the real onset of B-EGM (figure 3A).

155

156 *Automatic annotation (AUT-method)*

157 The annotation of LAT for each acquired point was automatically performed using the LAT
158 annotation tool integrated into CARTO3[®] system, called wavefront (WF). It uses the
159 maximum negative slope of the distal U-EGM to set the timing of the mapping annotation,
160 displayed on the corresponding B-EGM. The automatic annotation included the use of an
161 ECG recognition pattern algorithm, which is intended to avoid wrong annotation of
162 ventricular complexes other than the clinical PVC (figure 3B). The minimum percentage of

163 QRS similarity was set at $\geq 98\%$. If annotation was misleading due to the presence of atrial
164 far-field signals in the selected window of interest, manual elimination of the acquired point
165 was admitted.

166 In order to perform a comparative post-hoc analysis between the activation maps obtained
167 with the AUT- and MAN-methods, all cases were reannotated off-line using the alternative
168 annotation method. Manual reannotation was blinded to the AUT-maps.

169

170 **PVC ablation**

171 PVC ablation was directed to the EAS identified using the assigned annotation method. The
172 temperature limit was set in all cases at 45°C . Power limit was set according to the anatomical
173 structure containing the PVC-SOO: 50 W for the right ventricular outflow tract (RVOT) and
174 the subvalvular left ventricular outflow tract (LVOT), 40 W in the aortic root, 50 W for the
175 right ventricle, 50 W for the left ventricle, and 30 W in the coronary sinus. Ablation points
176 were always tagged using the VisiTag[®] feature included in CARTO3[®], setting a tag size of 4
177 mm in diameter. If a RF application was successful, it was maintained for a maximum of 45
178 seconds. The point (RFp) at which a RF application was successful to eliminate the PVCs was
179 tagged as the effective RFp (e-RFp). Any additional RF application located within a 5-mm
180 distance from the first application was considered as part of the same target point–suspected
181 SOO. On the contrary, all RF applications located beyond this 5-mm distance were
182 considered as additional target points.

183

184 **Clinical follow-up**

185 Clinical follow-up included an outpatient clinic visit one month after ablation procedure. 12-
186 lead ECG and 24-hour ambulatory Holter monitoring were performed. Clinical success was
187 defined as a reduction of $\geq 80\%$ in the 24-hour burden of PVCs within 6 months after

188 ablation, respectively. Antiarrhythmic drugs were routinely discontinued after the procedure,
189 except for those patients needing chronic betablocker therapy (i.e. those with prior structural
190 heart disease)

191

192 **Statistical analysis and sample size calculation**

193 For sample size calculation, a superiority design was assumed. Null hypothesis was
194 considered at the outset that the two annotation methods (MAN- and AUT-methods) are on
195 average equal in terms of mapping success (as previously defined), whereas the alternative
196 hypothesis stated that the proposed annotation methods are not equal. Based on historical
197 controls, the acute mapping success was considered would be 60% for manual annotation, and
198 85% for automatic annotation using the ECG pattern matching algorithm. The Type I error
199 was set to a value of 5%. The Type II error was set equal to 20%, with a statistical power of
200 80%. A sample size of 100 was estimated (50 patients per group). Randomization was
201 performed before ablation using the method of permuted block randomization. The block
202 sizes were randomly chosen as 4 and 6. Continuous variables are presented as mean values \pm
203 standard deviations, or median (interquartile range, IQR), as appropriate. Categorical
204 variables are presented as total numbers and percentages. To compare the means of 2
205 variables, the Student t-test or Wilcoxon test were used, as needed. Proportions were
206 compared using the χ^2 or Fisher exact test, when necessary. For agreement between manual
207 and automatic annotation at the EAS, Bland–Altman analysis was used. A p-value ≤ 0.05 was
208 considered for statistical significance. Statistics were obtained using IBM SPSS Statistics,
209 version 26.0 (IBM Corp. Released 2019; Armonk, NY: IBM Corp.).

210 **RESULTS**

211 Mean age was 56 ± 14 years, 54% men. The mean LVEF was $55 \pm 11\%$. Twenty-eight
212 patients (28%) had a previously diagnosed structural heart disease; from them, 18/28 (64%)
213 had a nonischemic cardiomyopathy with a mean LVEF of $42 \pm 6\%$. Mean NYHA class was
214 1.9 ± 0.6 points, and mean baseline PVC burden was $25 \pm 13\%$. Baseline characteristics were
215 similar between both study arms and are summarized in **table 1**. The most frequent PVC-SOO
216 were RVOT (41%), LV (25%), and LVOT (17%), with no MAN vs. AUT differences ($p =$
217 0.40) (**figure 4**). 25/58 (43%) cases with an OT origin showed a PVC-QRS with V3 transition;
218 for them, the use of a previously described clinical score ⁸ was used to decide which chamber
219 to map first (**figure 2**). In 11/25 (44%) of the cases with a LV origin the SOO was located at
220 the LV summit.

221

222 **Mapping comparison between MAN- and AUT-methods**

223 The propagation pattern, measured as 10-ms isochronal area, was similar between the groups
224 (1.29 ± 2.17 cm² AUT vs. 1.74 ± 2.28 cm² MAN; $p = 0.14$). With regards to the EAS
225 annotation, there was a significant good correlation in LAT between the AUT and MAN maps
226 ($r = 0.84$, $p < 0.001$; **figure 5A**). Further on, and in line with previous reports, ⁴ there was a
227 systematic delayed detection of LAT at the EAS in the AUT-arm (mean 22.36 ± 13.19 ms)
228 (**figure 5B**), especially in left-sided PVCs (27.94 ± 11.46 ms for left-sided vs. 17.49 ± 12.78
229 ms for right-sided PVCs, $p < 0.001$). Nevertheless, the median distance between the AUT-
230 EAS and MAN-EAS was only 3.1 mm (0 – 6.4 mm), with 33/100 (33%) of the patients
231 showing an inter-EAS distance < 1 mm.

232 There were 7 patients (7%) with an inter-EAS distance > 10 mm. The distribution of SOO
233 locations in these cases was: 3 LV, 2 RVOT, 1 LVOT, 1 RV; despite an increased inter-EAS
234 distance, the median distance between the e-RFp and the respective EAS was not significantly

235 different between the AUT and MAN maps [12.3 (4.6 – 15.6) mm vs. 4.4 (2.6 – 10.2) mm,
236 respectively; $p = 0.15$]. There was one case, assigned to the AUT-method, with an inter-EAS
237 distance of 20 mm; it corresponded to a patient with non-ischemic cardiomyopathy and peri-
238 Hisian PVCs related to the presence of septal intramyocardial fibrosis. The AUT-method
239 failed for some points due to wrong LAT annotation at atrial far-field signals. ⁴

240

241 **Procedure and clinical outcomes**

242 While the total number of RF applications and RF time were similar for both groups,
243 significantly more activation points at the activation maps were acquired in the AUT-arm
244 (table 2). On the other hand, mapping and procedure times were significantly shorter for the
245 AUT-arm when compared to the MAN-arm (table 2, graphical abstract).

246 Mapping success, as previously defined, was practically identical for both groups (62% AUT
247 vs. 60% MAN; $p = 0.84$). Acute procedure success was significantly better for the AUT-arm
248 (100% vs. 88%; $p = 0.01$), but without differences in clinical success during follow-up (92%
249 AUT vs. 88% MAN; $p = 0.51$) (graphical abstract). There were 4 patients in the AUT-arm
250 who did not meet the criteria for early clinical success despite a successful procedure; 2
251 corresponded to PVCs arising from the LV summit, 1 from the RVOT and 1 from the peri-
252 Hisian region.

253 Mean PVC burden after the end of follow-up was $2.9 \pm 5.1\%$, representing a mean burden
254 reduction of $85 \pm 29\%$, without differences between the AUT and MAN arms ($p = 0.78$). No
255 procedure-related complications were identified in any patient. Antiarrhythmic drugs were
256 routinely discontinued after the procedure, except betablockers for those patients (28/100,
257 28%) with prior structural heart disease.

258 **DISCUSSION**

259 **Main findings**

260 To the best of our knowledge, this is the first multicenter randomized study assessing the
261 possible benefits of a full-automated approach for PVC mapping (PVC-ECG recognition and
262 LAT annotation) during PVC ablation procedures, as compared with a conventional, manual
263 approach carried out by expert operators. The AUT-method comprises two tools, WF
264 annotation and an ECG pattern matching algorithm, already available in the CARTO3
265 electroanatomic navigation system. Although the primary endpoint of the study (mapping
266 success as previously defined) was equally achieved using both approaches, the AUT-method
267 was associated with a greater acute procedural success and similar clinical efficacy during
268 follow-up, and allowed to perform more efficient procedures in terms of mapping density and
269 procedure times, by permitting to acquire higher density maps in less time.

270

271 **Accuracy of bipolar and unipolar-based LAT annotation methods**

272 The aspect that determines to a greater extent the results of catheter ablation of PVCs is the
273 accuracy of LAT annotation during activation mapping. In this regard, the use of either B-
274 EGM or U-EGM-based annotations has some drawbacks. Briefly, the amplitude of B-EGMs
275 is influenced by the underlying substrate, direction of wavefront propagation, bipole
276 orientation, electrode size, and interelectrode spacing.^{1,2} Manual annotation of B-EGMs can
277 be challenging, particularly in cases of low-voltage signals or in the presence of multiple
278 components, a specially important aspect in LVOT-PVCs and fibrotic substrates.^{4,9} The
279 annotation at the onset of B-EGM has the advantage of delimiting an unequivocal signal, but
280 this method is still sensitive to far-field activation and may lead to less accurate activation
281 maps.^{3,10} As for U-EGMs, they contain significant far-field signal generated by
282 depolarization of remote tissue; further on, the typical unipolar QS complex sought at the

283 earliest activation site in focal arrhythmias may be also recorded when the exploring electrode
284 is not in sufficient contact with the underlying tissue.¹ Moreover, the type of U-EGM pattern
285 registered may be also related to the size of the mapping catheter.¹¹
286 In order to standardize the determination of LAT and improve the accuracy of activation
287 maps, several algorithmic methods were developed by El Haddad et al.³; one of them, based
288 on the maximal $-dV/dt$ in the U-EGM within the window demarcated by the B-EGM, reached
289 the highest accuracy and was integrated as a ready-to-use tool into CARTO3 navigation
290 system. The results of the present randomized study evaluating this tool permit to assess the
291 potential clinical benefit of the use of this algorithmic method, which we have referred to as
292 WF method.

293

294 **Utility of a full-automatic LAT annotation system during PVC ablation procedures**

295 The proposed automatic LAT annotation approach, named AUT-method, was not only based
296 in WF annotation, as previously discussed, but in its integration with an ECG pattern
297 matching algorithm to automatize the whole process of activation mapping. This last
298 algorithm allows to automatically annotate LAT each time the system detects a PVC which is
299 concordant to a previously acquired PVC-ECG reference, after setting a minimum % of
300 correlation in the 12-lead surface ECG. In this study, the lowest correlation was manually set
301 at 98%, thus avoiding wrong annotation of ventricular complexes other than the clinical PVC,
302 such as those resulting from inadvertent topo-stimulation with the mapping catheter.

303 Far beyond other technical aspects, such as the systematic delayed detection of LAT using
304 WF-annotation, which has been already recognized and discussed in previous studies,^{3,4} this
305 multicenter randomized study demonstrates that the full automatization of activation mapping
306 during PVC ablation procedures is feasible in the clinical practice, while being more efficient
307 than conventional, manual mapping.

308

309 **Study limitations:**

310 The results of this study cannot be applied to arrhythmia mechanisms other than focal, when
311 using multi-electrode or mini-electrode catheters to create activation maps, or when using
312 different navigation systems. Contact-force sensing technology was not systematically used;
313 therefore, its influence on automatic annotation cannot be determined. One of the limiting
314 aspects of WF annotation refers to the need to adjust the window of interest at the end of the
315 QRS to avoid the detection of far-field atrial signals; despite this, the presence of wrong
316 annotated points cannot be fully excluded. Finally, an automatic LAT annotation approach
317 critically depends on the quality of the unipolar signals; noisy signals (i.e. due to external
318 interferences) may cause obtention of misleading activation maps.

319

320 **Conclusions:**

321 During PVC ablation procedures, a full-automatic activation mapping method that uses an
322 ECG pattern matching algorithm plus WF annotation of LAT is feasible, reaching similar
323 mapping success and clinical outcomes when compared to a conventional, manual approach
324 carried out by expert operators. Automatic activation mapping is more efficient in terms of
325 mapping and procedure times, while allowing the acquisition of higher density maps.

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328

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332

333 **CONFLICT OF INTEREST**

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- 374

376 Table 1. Baseline characteristics.

	TOTAL (n = 100)	MAN-method (n = 50)	AUT-method (n = 50)	P-value
Age, years	56 ± 14	54 ± 15	58 ± 14	0.17
Men (%)	54 (54%)	30 (60%)	24 (48%)	0.23
Hypertension (%)	36 (36%)	15 (30%)	21 (43%)	0.21
Dyslipidemia (%)	78 (78%)	11 (22%)	11 (22%)	1.0
Diabetes mellitus (%)	9 (9%)	6 (12%)	3 (6%)	0.30
Active smoker (%)	11 (11%)	5 (10%)	6 (12%)	0.75
COPD (%)	3 (3%)	2 (4%)	1 (2%)	0.56
Clinical score^{*8}	1 (0 – 2)	1 (0 – 2)	1 (0 – 2)	0.98
No SHD	71 (71%)	36 (74%)	35 (70%)	0.57
LVEF (%)	55 ± 11	56 ± 11	55 ± 12	0.67
NYHA class (%)	1 (1 – 2)	1 (1 – 2)	1 (1 – 2)	0.31
Atrial fibrillation (%)	8 (8%)	4 (8%)	4 (8%)	1.0
Conduction disease (%)	14 (14%)	8 (16%)	6 (12%)	0.56
Pacemaker carrier (%)	3 (3%)	1 (2%)	2 (4%)	0.56
Baseline PVC burden (%)	25 ± 13	25 ± 14	25 ± 12	1.0
Sinus Rhythm QRS, ms	92 ± 18	92 ± 17	92 ± 19	1.0
PVC-QRS, ms	153 ± 28	147 ± 28	158 ± 28	0.05
PVC-LBBB morphology	81 (81%)	39 (80%)	42 (84%)	0.57
PVC coupling, ms	487 ± 91	482 ± 88	491 ± 94	0.62
Treatment				

• Betablockers	64 (64%)	31 (62%)	33 (66%)	0.68
• Amiodarone	8 (8%)	3 (6%)	5 (10%)	0.46
• Flecainide	3 (3%)	2 (4%)	1 (2%)	0.56
• ACEI/ARB	31 (31%)	13 (26%)	18 (36%)	0.28

377 *COPD: Chronic obstructive pulmonary disease; SHD: structural heart disease; LVEF: left*
378 *ventricular ejection fraction; NYHA: New York Heart Association; PVC: premature*
379 *ventricular complex; LBBB: left bundle branch block.*

380 **Statistically significant differences ($p < 0.05$).*

381 *†Clinical score to predict LVOT origin in PVCs with inferior axis and V3 transition. One*
382 *point is added for each of the following items: hypertension, male gender, age > 50 years.*
383 *The mean predicted LVOT probability is 15% for score 0, 26% for score 1, 60% for score 2,*
384 *and 87% for score 3 (Penela D, et al. Europace 2015;17:1122-1128).*

385

386

387 **Table 2.** Total mapping time, number of RF applications, RF time, and procedure time.

	TOTAL (n = 100)	MAN-method (n = 50)	AUT-method (n = 50)	P-value
Mapping time (min)	29.1 ± 13.9	32.8 ± 12.6	25.5 ± 14.3	0.009*
Total acquired points	103 (67 – 165)	79 (52 – 111)	136 (94 – 222)	< 0.001*
SOO acquired points	80 (51 – 135)	60 (35 – 80)	120 (81 – 188)	< 0.001*
N. of RF applications	2 (2 – 4)	2 (2 – 4)	2 (2 – 4)	0.91
RF time (sec)	90 (60 – 161)	90 (53 – 188)	90 (62 – 151)	0.86
Procedure time (min)	61.1 ± 25.7	67.4 ± 25.2	54.8 ± 24.8	0.014*

388 *SOO: Site of origin; RF: radiofrequency; MAN: manual; AUT: automatic.*

389 **Statistically significant differences ($p < 0.05$).*

390 **FIGURE LEGENDS**

391 **Graphical abstract.** Main findings of the study.

392 **Figure 1.** Diagram of study population.

393 **Figure 2.** *Panel A:* Algorithm to decide which chamber (RVOT vs. LVOT) to map first in
394 patients with PVCs of OT suspected origin. *Panel B:* Application of a previously described
395 clinical score ⁸ in OT-PVCs with V3 transition (n = 58) to predict the right vs. left SOO and
396 decide the first vascular access. 1 point is added for each of the following items: hypertension,
397 male gender, age > 50 years. With this approach, 12/18 (67%) patients with V3 transition and
398 a clinical score of 0-1 benefited from a single venous access, or from a single arterial access
399 in 5/7 (71%) with V3 transition and a clinical score of 2-3.

400 **Figure 3.** Example of manual vs. automatic annotation systems. The case corresponds to an
401 automatic-assigned case of LVOT-PVCs with blinded post-hoc manual reannotation. The 10-
402 ms isochronal areas are shown. The inter-EAS distance was 7 mm.

403 **Figure 4.** PVC-SOO distribution between the two study arms.

404 **Figure 5.** *Panel A:* Correlation in LAT annotation at the EAS between the AUT and MAN-
405 methods. *Panel B:* Bland–Altman plot showing agreement between automatic and manual
406 LAT annotations at the EAS identified.